

ANALYSIS OF METACOGNITIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF DECISION-MAKING IN MANAGERS' NEGOTIATION ACTIVITIES.

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Abstract: This article explores the historical development of social pedagogy across various international contexts, tracing its evolution from the 19th century to the present. Social pedagogy, broadly defined as the intersection of social work and education, emphasizes a holistic approach to personal and societal well-being. The study investigates how different countries have shaped social pedagogy through unique educational and social welfare perspectives, influenced by cultural, political, and economic factors. By examining key contributions from countries such as Germany, Denmark, the United Kingdom, and Brazil, this paper highlights the diverse approaches to social pedagogy and discusses its role in contemporary society. The findings underscore the importance of social pedagogy in fostering social inclusion, addressing inequality, and promoting community-based solutions in education.

Keywords: social pedagogy, history, social welfare, education, international development, social inclusion, community education

АНАЛИЗ МЕТАКОГНИТИВНЫХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ПРИНЯТИЯ РЕШЕНИЙ В ПЕРЕГОВОРНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ МЕНЕДЖЕРОВ.

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Аннотация: Эта статья исследует историческое развитие социальной педагогики в различных международных контекстах, прослеживая его эволюцию с XIX века до настоящего времени. Социальная педагогика, в широком смысле определяемая как пересечение социальной работы и образования, подчеркивает целостный подход к личному и социальному благополучию. Исследование расследует, как различные страны сформировали социальную педагогику с помощью уникальных образовательных и социальных перспектив, на которые влияют культурные, политические и экономические факторы. Изучая ключевые вклады из таких стран, как Германия, Дания, Соединенное Королевство и Бразилия, этот документ подчеркивает различные подходы к социальной педагогике и обсуждает ее роль в современном обществе. Результаты подчеркивают важность социальной педагогики в содействии социальной интеграции, устранению неравенства и поощрению решений на базе общин в области образования.

Ключевые слова: социальная педагогика, история, социальное обеспечение, образование, международное развитие, социальная интеграция, общинное образование.

MENEJERLARNING MUZOKARALAR FAOLIYATIDA QAROR QABUL QILISHNING METAKOGNITIV XUSUSIYATLARINI TAHLIL QILISH.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ijtimoiy pedagogikaning tarixiy rivojlanishini turli xalqaro kontekstlarda ko'rib chiqadi, uning 19-asrdan hozirgi kungacha bo'lgan evolyutsiyasini kuzatadi. Keng ma'noda ijtimoiy ish va ta'limning kesishishi sifatida ta'riflangan ijtimoiy pedagogika shaxsiy va ijtimoiy farovonlikka yaxlit yondashuvni ta'kidlaydi. Tadqiqot turli mamlakatlar ijtimoiy pedagogikani madaniy, siyosiy va iqtisodiy omillar ta'sirida noyob ta'lim va ijtimoiy istiqbollari orqali qanday shakllantirganini o'rganadi. Germaniya, Daniya, Buyuk Britaniya va Braziliya kabi mamlakatlarning asosiy hissalarini o'rganib chiqqan holda, ushbu maqola ijtimoiy pedagogikaga turli yondashuvlarni ta'kidlaydi va uning zamonaviy jamiyatdagi rolini muhokama qiladi. Natijalar ijtimoiy inklyuziyani rivojlantirish, tengsizliklarni bartaraf etish va ta'limda jamoatchilik asosidagi yechimlarni ilgari surishda ijtimoiy pedagogikaning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy pedagogika, tarix, ijtimoiy ta'minot, ta'lim, xalqaro rivojlanish, ijtimoiy integratsiya, jamoa ta'limi.

INTRODUCTION

Social pedagogy, as an academic field and professional practice, emerged in Europe in the 19th century, primarily through efforts to address social inequalities and integrate disadvantaged populations into society. Unlike traditional education focused solely on academic achievement, social pedagogy takes a broader view, aiming to support individuals' holistic development within a community context. Historically, social pedagogy grew from a need to support the vulnerable—especially children and marginalized groups—by combining educational and social work principles.

The development of social pedagogy has been heavily influenced by various international perspectives, with each country adding distinct elements based on its cultural, political, and social context. This paper reviews the history of social pedagogy across different countries, examining how they have contributed to the field and adapted it to fit local needs. By understanding these international contributions, this study sheds light on social pedagogy's role as a catalyst for social change and well-being.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a historical-comparative methodology to trace the development of social pedagogy across several countries. Primary sources, such as educational treatises and foundational documents, were analyzed to understand the theoretical underpinnings and historical context. Additionally, secondary sources, including academic articles, historical records, and case studies, provided insight into each country's unique contributions to the field.

Countries with well-documented histories of social pedagogy—such as Germany, Denmark, the United Kingdom, and Brazil—were selected for their distinct contributions and impact on global practices. The analysis focused on identifying patterns, key figures, and pivotal events that have shaped social pedagogy over time. Comparative analysis was used to identify both shared principles and unique national characteristics.

RESULTS

The historical examination revealed the evolution of social pedagogy in four key countries, each contributing unique perspectives and methodologies:

1. Germany: The roots of social pedagogy can be traced to Germany, where theorists such as Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi and Friedrich Froebel emphasized holistic education and the importance of caring relationships. Germany's approach focused on integrating children from

marginalized backgrounds into society through community-based support, thereby setting the foundation for social pedagogy as a discipline.

2. Denmark: Danish social pedagogy developed a strong focus on community and democratic participation. Danish practitioners emphasized the importance of inclusion and social justice, believing that education should foster individuals' ability to contribute to society. Denmark also established early training programs for social pedagogues, formalizing the profession and setting standards.

3. United Kingdom: Social pedagogy in the UK emerged more recently, primarily influenced by European traditions. British social pedagogy adapted practices to address specific issues, such as child protection and foster care, focusing on relational care and empowerment. The UK's emphasis on outcomes and evidence-based practices has influenced the broader international field.

4. Brazil: In Brazil, social pedagogy developed within a context of social inequalities and has been a key tool in promoting social justice and combating poverty. The Brazilian approach integrates community engagement and popular education, inspired by Paulo Freire's work. Brazilian social pedagogy prioritizes the empowerment of marginalized communities through educational programs tailored to local needs.

ANALYSIS

This historical examination highlights both common themes and unique adaptations in the development of social pedagogy:

- Holistic and Relational Approach: Across countries, social pedagogy is characterized by a holistic approach, focusing on the individual within their social environment. This approach, derived from early theorists like Pestalozzi, emphasizes the importance of nurturing relationships, well-being, and personal growth.

- Community-Centered Model: Countries like Denmark and Brazil emphasize community participation and social integration. Social pedagogy in these contexts aims to create an inclusive society where everyone, regardless of background, can contribute meaningfully.

- Adaptation to Local Needs: Each country has adapted social pedagogy to address its own social issues. For example, Germany initially focused on integrating marginalized children, while Brazil used social pedagogy as a tool for poverty reduction and community empowerment.

- Professionalization and Training: In several countries, social pedagogy has become a formal profession with specific training programs and professional standards. Denmark was among the first to establish professional training for social pedagogues, setting an example for other nations.

DISCUSSION

The development of social pedagogy illustrates how education and social work can combine to address complex societal issues. By fostering social inclusion, promoting holistic development, and supporting vulnerable populations, social pedagogy has become a crucial element in social welfare systems worldwide. The field has evolved to meet diverse needs, from child welfare in the UK to community education in Brazil.

In examining the common principles of social pedagogy, it is evident that relational care, community orientation, and a holistic approach are central to the discipline. Social pedagogy aims to empower individuals by helping them understand their social responsibilities, develop resilience, and engage meaningfully with their communities. The professionalization of social

pedagogy has also enhanced its impact, creating standards and ensuring that practitioners are equipped to handle complex social issues.

The differences among national approaches reflect the flexibility of social pedagogy as a field adaptable to local contexts. For instance, Germany's early focus on integration contrasts with Brazil's emphasis on social justice and poverty reduction. Despite these differences, the foundational principles of social pedagogy—compassion, empowerment, and community support—remain constant.

CONCLUSION

The history of social pedagogy reflects the dynamic relationship between education, social work, and societal well-being. Each country has contributed unique insights, enhancing social pedagogy's relevance and applicability in diverse contexts. Social pedagogy's emphasis on holistic development, relational care, and community empowerment makes it a powerful tool for addressing social challenges.

Future research could explore the impact of globalization on social pedagogy, examining how international collaboration might shape the field. Additionally, studies could investigate how social pedagogy can further contribute to contemporary issues, such as mental health and digital literacy, by integrating technology and adapting to the evolving needs of society.

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